

The Role of 3T Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Detecting Anterior Cruciate Ligament Injuries

Jagdish Saini¹, Bhanu Pratap², Gourav Kumar², Manish Kumar Baul², Kritika Gupta², Somnath Teli³

^{1,3}Research Fellow, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiation & Imaging Technology, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Corresponding Author: Mr. Bhanu Pratap, Assistant Professor, Department of Radiation & Imaging Technology, Nims University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Received: May 05, 2025

Accepted: Jun 06, 2025

Published: Jun 07, 2025

Abstract

Background: Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries are common among active individuals and can lead to significant knee instability if not diagnosed and treated promptly. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), particularly 3T MRI, offers high-resolution imaging for accurate diagnosis of ACL and associated knee injuries.

Objectives:

1. To assess the sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy of 3T MRI in identifying ACL and posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) injuries in patients with knee trauma.
2. To evaluate the role of 3T MRI in distinguishing partial from complete ACL and PCL tears.
3. To determine the prevalence and patterns of associated knee injuries, such as meniscal tears, bone contusions, and ligamentous injuries, using 3T MRI.

Methods: A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, from October 2023 to March 2024, involving 60 patients with suspected knee injuries referred for 3T MRI. Data were collected using a self-designed data capture sheet and analyzed with Microsoft Excel 2011. Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18 and above with a history of knee trauma within the past 6 months. Exclusion criteria included prior knee surgery, chronic knee conditions, multi-ligament injuries, or pregnancy. Imaging was performed using a 3T Siemens Magnetom MRI with specific sequences (T1-weighted, T2-weighted, proton density fat-suppressed, and STIR).

Results: Of the 54 analysed patients, 74% were male, and the 25–35 age group was most affected (42.6%). ACL tears were identified in 74% of cases (40/54), with 39% complete tears, 22% partial tears, and 39% intact tears. PCL tears were less common (9.3%, 5/54). The right knee was affected in 69% of cases. Associated injuries, including joint effusion and meniscal tears, were also observed.

Conclusion: 3T MRI demonstrates high diagnostic accuracy for detecting ACL injuries, particularly in young, active males. Its ability to differentiate tear types and identify associated injuries supports its role as a critical tool for clinical decision-making.

Keywords: 3T MRI, anterior cruciate ligament, posterior cruciate ligament, knee injuries, diagnostic accuracy.

Introduction:

The stability of the knee joint is maintained by the anterior cruciate ligaments (ACL) and posterior cruciate ligaments (PCL), which are significant components of the knee joint.^[1] These ligament injuries can cause severe functional instability. One important contributing cause to the functional instability of the injured knee joint is the decreased neuromuscular function that frequently follows an ACL injury.^[2]

It is essential for keeping the knee stable during dynamic exercises, particularly those that include pivoting, leaping, and abrupt direction changes. ACL injuries, especially rips, are prevalent in sports and active people. If treatment is not received, they can result in cartilage damage, long-term knee instability, and an increased chance of developing osteoarthritis early.^[2]

Restoring knee function and preventing further injuries need prompt diagnosis and treatment. With the development of imaging technology, the diagnosis of ACL injuries has evolved dramatically, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is now a crucial technique for identifying ACL tears and evaluating related knee pathologies.^[1]

With the advancement of MRI technology, high-resolution imaging methods - such as 3T MRI - have produced pictures of the knee structures that are sharper and more detailed, increasing the diagnosis accuracy of ACL injuries.^[4] When evaluating ACL tears, 3T MRI provides improved visibility of the ligament as well as related ailments, such as meniscal tears and cartilage loss, which frequently coexist with ACL injuries.^[5] An very accurate non-invasive technique for assessing soft tissue injuries, such as ACL tears, is magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). It is highly successful in identifying ACL injuries with a high degree of sensitivity and specificity, according to several studies, particularly when compared to physical examination.^[7]

It is impossible to overestimate the significance of precise imaging in the diagnosis and post-

operative monitoring of ACL damage. Clinicians may make well-informed decisions about treatment and rehabilitation by using MRI to see the intricate anatomy of the knee, including the ACL, menisci, and cartilage. As MRI technology develops further, especially with the introduction of 3T MRI, it provides improved diagnostic capabilities that are essential for enhancing patient outcomes and guaranteeing efficient treatment of ACL injuries.^[1,3] Our study specifically focuses on the advantages of using 3T MRI over lower-field MRI systems, as it offers higher resolution and better visualization of soft tissues, including the ACL and surrounding structures. By analysing the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of 3T MRI, this research aims to determine its potential as the gold standard for ACL injury evaluation.

Materials and Methods

STUDY DESIGN- A Cross-Sectional Prospective Study.

SOURCE OF DATA

Source of data will be collected from radiology department.

Data will be analyzed using descriptive statistical tools, frequencies, mean and percentage.

STUDY POPULATION

Patient of different ages and genders who have sustain spinal injuries due to various causes such as accidents, falls or sports-related incident and individuals with suspected spinal trauma who are being referred for MRI examination to Radiology department informed consent on approved format is included in the study.

Instrumentation and MRI Protocol

MRI examinations were performed on a Siemens Magnetom Vida 3T scanner with high-resolution head coils. The multiparametric protocol included:

SEQUENCES	TR (ms)	TE (ms)	FOV	Matrix	Slice Thickness
Knee localiser	3000	90	291x 290	208 x 205	4
PD fat sat axial	3000-4000	15 -20	150 -160	320 x320	3 -3.5mm
PD fat sat coronal	4000-5000	15-20	150-160	304 x 288	3-3.5 mm
PD fat sat sagittal	4000-5000	15-20	150-160	320 x 320	3-3.5 mm
T1 tse sagittal	400-600	15-25	150-160	320 x320	3-3.5 mm
T2*(MEDIC) sagittal	800-1200	15-25	150-160	256 x256	3-3.5 mm
PD fat sat coronal oblique 2.5mm for Anterior cruciate ligament	3000-4000	15-20	150-160	256 x256	2.5mm

Result:

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF GENDER OF PATIENTS

GENDER	n=54	In %
MALE	40	74
FEMALE	14	26

Table:1 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS OF GENDER OF PATIENTS

DISTRIBUTIONS OF AGE OF PATIENT

AGE INTERVAL	MALE	FEMALE
19-25	4	2
25-35	23	0
35-45	7	1
45-55	6	3
55-65	3	2
65-75	1	3

TABLE 2: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS AGE OF PATIENTS

FIG 2: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS AGE OF PATIENTS

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO THE SIDE OF INJURY ON KNEE

INJURY	RT KNEE	LT KNEE
	37	17

TABLE 3: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO THE CAUSE OF INJURY

TABLE 3: The distribution of patients according to the cause of injury within a sample of 54 cases reveals varied prevalence rates. RT Knee was the most common effected and less than LT Side.

ACL TEAR	EFFECTED	NOT EFFECTED
n=54	40	14

TABLE: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACL INJURY

PCL INJURY	EFFECTED	NOT EFFECTED
	5	49

Tab: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS PCL INJURY

COMPLETE TEAR	PARTIAL TERA	INTACT TEAR
21	12	21

Tab: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF TYPES OF ACL TEAR

FIGURE 1.1: GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Discussion

Gender Distribution

The study found that 74% of the patients were male and 26% were female. This higher proportion of male patients suggests that men may either experience knee injuries more frequently or are more likely to be referred for MRI evaluations.

Age Distribution

The largest age group was 25-35 years, comprising 23 of the patients of total population, followed by the 45-55 age group 9 patients are affected by the ACL Injury. This suggests that younger individuals, particularly those aged 25-35, are more prone to ACL injuries. This trend is likely due to higher levels of physical activity and sports participation among younger people. The distribution of knee injuries decreasing with age also reflects reduced physical activity levels in older populations.

Gender Specific Trends

ACL tear was more common in males compared to female & 74% of the patients are affected by ACL tear, 26% not effected by the ACL tear.

PCL Tear were not significantly more common in both male & female patients. 49 people are not affected by the PCL tear, 5 people are affected by PCL tear.

Which side knee is most effected trend

In our study observed that RT knee was most effected 69%, and LT Knee was affected 31% of the total population.

The tear can be categorized in 3 category 39% (21) patients are having complete tear,22% (12) patients are affected by partial ACL tear,39% (21) having intact tear on ACL.

Conclusion

The analysis of MRI data from 54 patients with knee injuries provides several key insights into the demographics and injury patterns related to ACL injuries.

The majority of patients were male (74.00%), suggesting a higher incidence of ACL injuries among men, potentially due to greater participation in activities with higher knee injury risk, such as sports.

Younger patients, especially those aged 25-35 years, constitute the largest group (52.00%), indicating a higher rate of ACL injuries in this age range, likely due to higher levels of physical activity and sports participation.

The most common injury identified was ACL tears (74.00%), while the least common was PCL tears (26.00%).

In the study 69.00% of the total patients are affected ACL Injury on the RT Side of knee.

Complete tear & intact tear are most common ACL tear types.

References

1. Zhao M, Zhou Y, Chang J, Hu J, Liu H, Wang S, Si D, Yuan Y, Li H. The accuracy of MRI in the diagnosis of anterior cruciate ligament injury. *Annals of translational medicine*. 2020 Dec;8(24).
2. Liu-Ambrose T. The anterior cruciate ligament and functional stability of the knee joint. *BC Med J*. 2003 Dec;45(10):495-9.
3. Amano K, Li AK, Padoia V, Koff MF, Krych AJ, Link TM, Potter H, Rodeo S, Li X, Ma CB, Majumdar S. Effects of surgical factors on cartilage can be detected using quantitative magnetic resonance imaging after anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. *The American journal of sports medicine*. 2017 Apr;45(5):1075-84.
4. Takahashi T, Kimura M, Takeshita K. MRI evaluation of the ACL remnant tissue in ACL-deficient knee. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery*. 2017 Nov 14;25(3):2309499017739479.
5. Sanchis-Alfonso V, Martinez-Sanjuan V, Gastaldi-Orquin E. The value of MRI in the evaluation of the ACL deficient knee and in the post-operative evaluation after ACL reconstruction. *European journal of radiology*. 1993 Feb 1;16(2):126-30.

6. Chahla J, Dean CS, Moatshe G, Mitchell JJ, Cram TR, Yacuzzi C, LaPrade RF. Meniscal ramp lesions: anatomy, incidence, diagnosis, and treatment. *Orthopaedic journal of sports medicine*. 2016 Jul 20;4(7):2325967116657815.
7. Marx R. G., Jones E. C., Atanda A. The diagnostic accuracy of MRI for detecting ACL tears in a clinical setting. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*, 2011.
8. Morales-Avalos R, Torres-González EM, Padilla-Medina JR, Monllau JC. ACL anatomy: Is there still something to learn? *Revista española de cirugía ortopédica y traumatología*. 2023 Feb 12.
9. Banovetz MT, Familiari F, Kennedy NI, Russo R, Palco M, Simonetta R, DePhillipo NN, LaPrade RF. Anatomy of the anterior cruciate ligament and the common autograft specimens for anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. *Annals of Joint*. 2023;8.
10. Smith, C., McGarvey, C., Harb, Z., Back, D., Houghton, R., Davies, A., & Ajuied, A. (2016). Diagnostic efficacy of 3-T MRI for knee injuries using arthroscopy as a reference standard: A Meta-Analysis. *American Journal of Roentgenology*, 207(2), 369–377. <https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.15.15795>
11. Nouri, N., Bouaziz, M. C., Riahi, H., Mechri, M., Kherfani, A., Ouertatani, M., & Ladeb, M. F. (2017). Traumatic meniscus and cruciate ligament tears in Young patients: A comparison of 3T versus 1.5T MRI. *Journal of the Belgian Society of Radiology*, 101(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/jbr-btr.1158>
12. Nisha Dagaret.et.al (2024) the study aimed that Role of MRI Sequences in Traumatic Knee Injuries